

A Different Look at Behavioral Research on the Psychology of Religion

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Abstract

Many of the first founders and political leaders of many countries were concerned with religious issues, and some of these concerns continue in science today. The religion of religion has a long history in the psychology of many countries, but it has been tainted by neglect and false claims about the nature of research. The religion of religion supplies an opportunity for behavioral research to be extended to many areas of psychology interest. For example, the consequences of both growth during adolescence and sex differences can be clarified by discussing the function of religion in the human being. Among the specific topics explored are conversion and religious mobility, religious experiences. Representations of God include identity and mental health and coping. Just a generation ago, psychologists and scholars often seemed to conclude that the world was steadily moving beyond religions. The word "post-Christian" was widely heard in intellectual circles. This trend is also reflected in the field of psychology, due to the lack of a research field called the psychology of religion. It has not existed since the founding of psychology in the 1900s by William James et al., who devoted some of their psychological work to the analysis of religiosity (for a comprehensive account of the history of the field, see Wul , 1997). But the science of psychology of religion did not return until the 1960s. The Study of the Psychology of Religion Then and Today Although psychology was the study of human behavior and mental processes, the field seemed to study all major human behavior except what was labeled "religious." This has seemed like a really challenging problem to many scientists. Why would the academic field of

psychology choose to ignore the fact that religiosity has been a part of human existence in one form or another since human beings have existed, and that throughout human history, religiosity has been a part of human existence? The most salient issues and sources of both human concern, help, and service to others, as well as human depravity, harm, and exploitation of others, are a few considerations. Psychology studies everything else there is to know about human behavior, as well as it. According to recent estimates, about 85 percent of the world's population either practices religion on a personal level or lives in a religiously sanctioned state. Much of people's lives are affected to some extent by their commitment to a religious tradition. Fortunately, there has been a surge in interest in working in this field in recent years. Examining some of the facts supporting this model, this article also draws on the literature.

Keywords: *Religion Psychology, Behavioral Studies, Function of Religion, Human Behavior, Mental Processes, Psychology*

1. Introduction

some capacity, many areas had begun to "go online" in the years leading up to the terrorist attacks on the World Trade Center in New York on September 11, 2001, which resulted in the deaths of nearly three thousand innocent citizens . The newly formed International Association for the Psychology of Religion (IAPR) was in its infancy in the 1990s, and several textbooks began to be published around the same time. In 1976 the American Psychological Association (APA) set up and appointed a chapter specifically for the study of religion (APA Chapter 36). ¹However, the field was still very independent; Psychologists working in religion communicated almost exclusively among themselves, and there was relatively little communication about their findings with those working in other fields of psychology. It has received limited attention from mainstream

¹ (For a summary of this history, see Emmons & Paloutzian, 2003).

psychology, and only a small part of current congressional time is spent discussing it in professional meetings. Much has changed since the September 11 terrorist attacks. Research, presentations and publications on topics related to the psychology of religion soon began to gain momentum on a steep slope (Paloutzian , 2017a, 2017b; Saroğlu , 2014). Although acts of terrorism were not in themselves inspired by a particular religion, they seemed justified in the name of the perpetrators' respective religious beliefs. One of the effects of this was that researchers in the more traditional branches of psychology began to study the mental processes associated with different types of religiosity (religious fundamentalism), (Altemeyer & Hunsberger , 2005; Rowatt et al., 2013), prosocial and antisocial behavior (Galen, 2012) conduct studies on terrorism (Moghaddam et al., 2013) and many other socially important genres. included . Two study notes supply evidence of the expanded amount of research being conducted in this area.

2. Number of Inclusions of the Words "Religion" and "Spirituality"

First, Saroglou (2014) looked at articles published in personality and social psychology journals and found how many times the word "religion" or "spirituality" appeared in article titles and abstracts. Second, Paloutzian (2017b), PsycInfo looked at the abstracts and titles of the articles for all items in the database . He discovered that between 2005 and 2014, the number of times the words "religion" and "spirituality" appeared in the abstracts or titles of articles increased sixfold. Both studies mentioned above point to two different inclusive trends. First, in the years before the terrorist attacks of September 11, 2001, there was a slight increase in people's interest in the psychology of religion (and later in the psychology of spirituality).

"This can be explained by a new generation of psychologists who have decided that this topic is important, manifestations include APA Chapter 36, the emergence of the IAPR , and early writings on the cognitive science of religion." Second, there was a sharp increase in the number of

publications in this field around the time of 9/11. There can be no other explanation other than the global and local side effects of the events of September 11, 2001.

Research on the psychological origins of religiosity, like other research on the psychological origins of religiosity, must be done seriously. If we were to construct a comprehensive, valid theory of all human behavior, and psychologists who had not done research on the subject in the past, they were eventually convinced that it had to be done.

3. An Overview of the Countries of the World

Journal in 1998 for the It is difficult to be editor of Psychology of Religion and continue in that capacity for the next 18 years (IJPR). It was the largest growth of the field during this period. Every day, exchanging emails with writers from all over the world, from various parts of Europe to other continents, is another task.

The following places can be found on the list:

Alaska, Australia, Austria, Brazil, Canada, China, Czech Republic, Denmark, England, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hong Kong, Iran, Israel, Italy, Japan, Jordan, Kenya, Kurdistan, Latvia, Netherlands, Northern Ireland, Norway, Malaysia, Malta, Mexico, Nigeria, Pakistan, Poland, Portugal, Russia, Saudi Arabia, Singapore, South Africa, Spain, Sweden, Taiwan, Thailand, Turkey, Ukraine, United Arab Emirates and others.

This is a completely new idea; Nothing like this has ever been said in the past. This is probably the result of a combination of the initiation of religiously motivated terrorist acts and the development of communication over the Internet.

4. Brazilian Example

Due to limitations imposed by the Brazil Sample Sheet space, it is not possible to supply a sample of work or mention a researcher from each of the countries where psychology of religion scholarship was held (for more examples, see Paloutzian, 2017a). I have room to elaborate on such a scenario and incidentally it comes from Brazil.²

Brazilian Professor Luciana Marques and I Spiritual Well-Being A conversation about conducting research using the Scale (SWBS; Paloutzian & Ellison , 1982; Paloutzian , Buord , & Wildman , 2012) has been noted (Marques , LF, Sarriera , C. and Dell'aglio , 2009). Later, as editor of IJPR , the decision was made to invite someone to author an article for the journal that would serve as a status report describing the research on psychology of religion being conducted in Brazil. After all, Professors Marques and Mary Rute Esperandio accepted his request to co-write the article as a team and they worked on it together. It was published in the October 2015 issue of IJPR (Volume 25, issue 4) and the topic of the article is "The Psychology of Religion in Brazil" . It should not be forgotten that it is not just a documentary consisting of descriptive information about who did what and where. Instead, it is based on the psychological and theoretical concerns that underpin the study. Thus, it not only tells people what is going on in Brazil, but also touches upon the psychological challenges common to working in the field of psychology of religion conducted by counterpart researchers in other nations and languages. This example has been discussed many times with scholars from other countries , and it would be correct to suggest that they follow the example of Esperandio and Marques to prepare an article documenting the current state of the psychology of religion in their country.

The foundation for an international partnership between psychologists studying religion in Brazil has been laid. Not only is it possible with the technology we have today, but it can also be quite

² Rev. _ runway Prax. theol . pastor. Curitiba , vol. 9, n. 1, 15-30, january/ abr. 2017 Psychology of Religion in a Global Context, Chapter 19

fun. The Application of Psychology to Religious Studies in the World Scripture, Religious Practices and Spirituality It is essential to make a distinction between discussing religion or religiosity from a psychology perspective and approaching the subject from a more general or more general humanities and social sciences perspective. People talk about religion in everyday language, and everyone seems to be aware of what is being said, even if they don't believe in the same belief. While there are historical, social and even legal reasons why some people or countries define the concept of " religion", there is not much consensus on what "religion" is, which is unfortunately quite unfortunate.³

are many concepts as ghosts, saints and deceased loved ones who are believed to " live" after death or in the spirit realm . Others argue that there is no need for such an otherworldly belief. For example, they point out that Buddhism, which is generally considered one of the "global religions," does not reveal a deity in its core texts. Also, what people call religions takes precedence in quite diverse ways. For example, in Protestant Christianity the emphasis is on believing in the right doctrine, while in Roman Catholic Christianity there is less emphasis on the confession and acceptance of the church's tenants, as well as the participation in the Eucharist , on the content of the emphasis in Judaism. Beliefs and more are on the observance of prescribed rituals and in Islam the emphasis is placed on the so-called "5 pillars of Islam".

A widely accepted point in the field of religious studies is that "religions", although they have some common elements, do not all focus on the same subject (Taves , 2013). The results of attempts to define "religion" or "spirituality" in the name of psychological work are not significantly different. The most used definition of religion in psychology defines it as "the desire to gain prominence in ways connected with the sacred" (Pargament , 1992). But these efforts at definition also show that everything can be sacred to anyone, regardless of context. Pargament et al. (2013), for example, only things like a person's god, a "spiritual" value, or something else

³ (Rev. Piste _ Prax. theol . pastor. Curitiba , vol. 9, n. 1, 15-30, January/April 2017)

personally meaningful can be sacred to someone, even war can satisfy someone's "spiritual" need. Other examples of things that might be sacred to someone include a personally meaningful object. Since there is no writing before the term "sacred", it can be concluded that the statement is not true. If one wishes, anything can be made sacred. The rationale behind this is that anyone can accept anything as a religion. There is no fundamental part that unifies many efforts to define what "it" is. It is often best to define religion as a complex cultural concept with specific meanings varying from culture to culture and even person to person (Taves, 2015).

This is probably the most accurate way to think about religion. And it is precisely these meanings that the psychological study of religiosity looks to explain—not "religion" itself. This does not mean that psychologists must settle for the "all is well" idea of what religiosity is; however, it does mean that we need to delve deeper into the psychological meanings that underpin it. Specifically, it means that we need to explore the relationship between religiosity and one's sense of self-worth.

5. Meaning Construction, Religious Meaning Structures and the Process of Change

Meaning making is a term that must be deciphered before we can begin to understand the psychological underpinnings of many meanings⁴, including those associated with religion.

The process of a system that receives information with varying degrees of uncertainty and processes that information in such a way that the output of the process is a perceptible, assessable, or responsible whole is called meaning-making. Meaning making is a process by which a system buys information. "At the output" is the meaning derived from the onslaught of confusing information. Such outputs tend to be endowed with religious, spiritual, or non-religious meanings.

⁴ (Rev. Piste _ Prax. theol . pastor. Curitiba , vol. 9, n. 1, 15-30, january/ abr. 2017 Psychology of Religion in Different Cultures and Countries 21)

Here are a few examples of how meaning is created by our systems, some quite simple and others quite complex.

6. A Perception in Human Consciousness

This is a considerably basic example when certain wavelengths of the electromagnetic spectrum enter the human eye through the pupil, strike the rods and cones in the retina, and activate brain impulses that cause the visual system to generate a perception in human consciousness. For example, scientifically speaking, the human eye does not "see" an apple on the table, even if it is there. In fact, the eye does nothing but relay confusing information to the next layer of neuronal tissue in the brain's visual system, and ultimately, these brain processes create a perception of something "out there", called an "apple." " But the apple we 'see' is an apple formed by our meaning-construction system, not the apple that exists (allegedly) 'out there.' As outlined above, the process of meaning creation, albeit in different guises and manifestations, is the entire human system, from the most minute to the broadest levels. (Paloutzian , 2017a; Paloutzian & Mukai , 2017). Imagine the processes that must be involved in how an entire person or large group makes sense out of the myriad uncertainties that exist in life. Something as basic as seeing, people need to make sense out of uncertainty. Just think of the processes that seeing must involve, or the feeling of uncertainty that arises when looking at the stars and wondering what the whole universe is like.

Or, when faced with the unpredictability of mortality, different things can be expressed for the definition of the feeling dimension. Do any of these have any meaning, or do any of them have only one meaning? Are there many comments? Might it be the "correct" meaning for me, but you might have a different "proper" meaning? These are timeless questions. They have been asked since the beginning of time. While psychology cannot answer these questions, it can shed light on the mechanisms at work and help us understand how they work. The same can be said for other religious meaning systems. An entity like this is a cognitive web of things like values and goals,

greater goals, a sense of identity, a general worldview, evaluation processes in which added information is evaluated and kept or rejected, some implicit or explicit position.⁵

To move forward in one's life, one must be able to digest added information or change and adapt to it. People who follow a particular religion tend to have an ultimate center of concern, either the religion itself or the principles it upholds. The rest of the person's system works as it should because it is managed by this system (Park, 2010). Meaning systems are typically quite stable, but they are also capable of going through transformations. A religious meaning system to which one is passionately and consistently dedicated (in a way that enables the individual to act in harmony with purported beliefs) offers the continuity necessary to view life over a period of time. The interests, values, identity and ultimate concern of the system are taken into account, when possible, by us, directly or indirectly, when making a choice. This reflects the concept that individuals need a coherent and well-functioning meaning system to survive at both the biological and psychological levels (Park, 2010, 2013).

Of course, systems of meaning need not be religious; For those who believe in such religions, there are atheistic and agnostic analogues that can work psychologically in the same way as religious meaning systems run (Bullivant and Ruse , 2013). This means that the basic processes of human belief are at the core of systems of meaning. This does not necessarily refer to religious belief; rather, it refers to belief in general. (For a detailed discussion of the many components involved in believing processes , see Angel et al., 2017). This shows that the psychology of religion is not a separate field of its own that runs in a vacuum. It is an integral part of the whole scientific study of psychology; in fact, it is inextricably linked to the body of knowledge produced by disciplines running at both the micro and macro level.

⁵ System Rev. _ runway Prax. theol . pastor. Curitiba , Vol 9, N. 1, 15-30, January/April 2017
Paloutzian , Fr 22

Since religiosity is both an individual and a social phenomenon, we need to combine the knowledge gained from the fields of psychology and anthropology to fully understand it. This is just an example. And from that point on, the argument extrapolates.

7. Multi-Level International and Interdisciplinary Research Paradigm

At some point in the future, our understanding of human religiosity will no longer be constrained by discipline. Instead, we will generate new knowledge while working under the auspices of a multidimensional, multinational and multidisciplinary paradigm . This means that we will conduct any research necessary, using a wide variety of research methods, to understand the fundamental meanings of people's religious beliefs, rituals, codes of conduct and associations, and the like ; and with contributions from biology, psychology, anthropology and other related fields, we would learn about such things in all cultures and religions of the world.⁶

At this time, an extended level would be considered an ideal. ²³ Psychology of Religion in the World However, the need to achieve this goal is compelling. The following two issues that periodically appear in the psychology of religion literature highlight the need for a single, unified framework rather than a set of frameworks within which people can move forward.

8. Religion \Atheism

Ever since humans first set foot on the surface of the planet, they have wondered about their origins, why they are on earth, and their significance. Much of a society's efforts to find answers to such problems are directed through its religious practices. Although he is not always successful

⁶ Rev. _ runway Prax. theol . pastor. Curitiba , vol. 9, n. 1, 15-30, january./ abr. 2017; Rev. _ runway Prax. theol . pastor. curitiba _

in achieving this goal, he is often successful in giving his followers a sense of structure, ethical code, and purpose. Because this belief fulfills a crucial psychological need, adherents are also strongly motivated to believe in the possibility of an afterlife, a fundamental tenet of most organized religions.

Beliefs in religion are a manifestation of our exceptional cognitive ability to see action and purpose in other people and, by extension, in the natural world. The earliest forms of religious thought were pantheistic; this meant that they attributed the same kinds of supernatural powers to elements of the natural world as they do today. Religion has kept pace with the increasing complexity of social groupings and the formation of permanent communities since the beginning of agriculture, and this trend continues. Their rituals and beliefs promote social cohesion and group identity, even if they sometimes exclude people who disagree with the adherents of those beliefs and rituals .

9. Why Do People Think God Exists?

According to evolutionary psychology, the belief that gods exist may have arisen as humans mastered the use of tools, developed a sense of agency, and then applied that concept to the world around them, if a higher power must have created it. This would lead to the assumption that the gods handled the world. Even if most people in today's world have a solid grasp of the science that underpins the natural world, a sizable minority still cling to the idea that there is a god who gives purpose to the universe.

10. Is Religion Beneficial or Harmful to Humans?

Is religion beneficial to humanity? For decades, psychologists have debated the answer to this question. Some people believe that being affiliated with a religious institution is different from

having a personal spiritual practice, and they place more emphasis on the latter. However, a substantial amount of research shows that people's religious beliefs and commitment can help them cope with stress, and many individuals derive great benefits from the social support offered by their religious communities. On the other hand, this can have a negative effect, especially if those who hold firm beliefs internalize feelings of shame and guilt.

11. Advantages of Having Faith

A person's spiritual beliefs can help their health, increase their hope and resilience, while also reducing their risk for clinical depression, drug use, suicide, and other dangerous behaviors. Faith has the power to unite people whose values overlap, to provide these individuals with a sense of belonging and increased social support. In addition, many religious organizations supply financial aid to health-related projects that have a good impact on their communities. These efforts include healthy eating, regular exercise, and stress reduction.

People can find solace in their faith in tough times, especially when they have suffered a significant loss. It gives people a reason to live and a basis for their morals, both as a deterrent from doing wrong. A child's religious upbringing can encourage them to be more charitable, which is a benefit not only for the child but also for the parent. Compared to their friends who are agnostic or atheist, religious youth are much more likely to be active in community outreach activities such as volunteering and are significantly more likely to name forgiveness as a preferred value.

12. Is It Possible for Religious Faith to Help Protect Against Depression?

Religiosity has been found to significantly reduce the risk of either the onset or relapse of depression in people who are already at elevated risk for this condition, either because they have

parents who suffer from depression or because they have had depression themselves. How religion can supply such a benefit is still being explored, but one possible answer is that it helps people become more resilient.

religious engagement can bring significant benefits to both the body and mind. Consistent attendance at religious services has been associated with improved physical and mental health , including longer and more restful sleep, lower blood pressure, and a reduced risk of premature death . People who regularly attend religious services have been shown to have a lower risk of "death from despair", such as committing suicide or accidentally overdosing on drugs or alcohol.

13. Psychology and Religious Beliefs

A movement in the field of psychotherapy argues that although religious beliefs are essential components of many people's identity and help shed light on the sources of their struggles, some therapists should not exclude religion from their sessions with patients. However, some therapists still do this. When doing therapy with a client, it may be helpful to include some aspects of the client's belief system or practices. This can help the client better understand and accept therapeutic counselling.

According to recent surveys and research, a much smaller percentage of individuals today look to religious or spiritual authorities for advice or instruction than decades ago. In the absence of such a connection , they may be more likely to turn to therapists as "wise figures" who can play a key role in their lives , especially if the clinician is able to include the client's belief system in their discussion. This is especially true if the clinician can provide the client with a sense of control over the therapeutic process.

Spirituality and religion have been found to be positive indicators of one's own sense of well-being, although the findings of different studies do not always agree. This conflicting evidence is

likely attributable to inadequate functionalization of structures, as well as to neglecting the softening effect an individual's religious status can have on the link between spirituality or religiosity and subjective well-being levels. The aim of this study is to investigate the relationship between spirituality and religiosity and the individual's subjective well-being (defined here as the balance between both life satisfaction and positive and negative affect) and to evaluate whether there are differences according to the individual's lifestyle status (religious, non-religious and ambiguous) . The purpose of this study was to explore the relationship between spirituality (defined here as focusing on one's purpose, interiority, connection, and transcendence) and religiosity (defined here as focusing on three dimensions of one's religious identity).

14. Engagement, Deep Discovery, and Reassessment of Engagement

Models related to spirituality were evaluated on the whole sample and the results showed that spirituality has a positive effect on subjective well-being (except for the Interconnection dimension) and the individual's religious status, not religious status. It is possible to evaluate any effect on this relationship with many literature models. Models related to religiosity were evaluated only on religious and insecure individuals, and the researchers revealed that the relationship between religiosity and subjective well-being differs according to the religious status of the individual. For example, the primary distinction we discovered is that adherence to a religious identity positively predicts life enjoyment only among religious people, but not among individuals whose religious beliefs are ambiguous. Findings are interpreted and the results of these interpretations are examined.

Subjective well-being, commonly known as SWB, refers to how individuals feel about the caliber of their own lives (Diener , 1984; Stratham & Chase, 2010). This assessment consists of cognitive part and affective component (Diener , 1984; Luhmann , 2017; Diener et al., 2018). Cognitive part refers to the cognitive judgments related to the achievement of important values and goals

throughout the life span of the individual, while the affective part refers to the balance between positive and negative affect. Both components are discussed in Diener's research (Luhmann et al., 2012a,b). Thus, subjective well-being (SWP) refers to long-term levels of happiness that result from a general self-assessment of one's overall satisfaction with one's life (e.g., Diener, 1984) and whether people are living a good lifestyle (Diener and Seligman, 2004; Diener et al., 2009a; Diener, 2012). (“Frontiers | The Role of Spirituality and Religiosity in Subjective Well ...”)

Affective dimension of SS, presence of positive well-being in research (eg, happiness; Sagiv & Schwartz, 2000; Pollard & Lee, 2003), prevalence of positive affect (eg, Positive and Negative Impact Chart (PANAS), Watson et al., 1988; Positive and Negative Experience Scale (SPANE), Diener et al., 2009b) or absence of negative emotion (eg, Cummins, 2013). Both the Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS; Diener et al., 1985), which refer to a global assessment of life satisfaction, and the Personal Well-Being Index (PWI; Cummins and Lau, 2004) have been used to measure life satisfaction, the cognitive part of subjective well-being. Both scales were developed by Diener and colleagues in 1985 (Lai et al., 2013).

There are several factors that can contribute to and influence a person's assessment of numerous aspects of their life. These factors can range from individual characteristics that distinguish happy and unhappy personalities, to values that people find important and worth pursuing in life, or to meeting social needs (Balzarotti et al., 2016; Diener et al., 2018; Schwartz & Sortheix, 2018). A growing body of research is exploring, among other things, the role of spirituality and religiosity in individuals' self-perceived well-being. This research has shown that religion and spirituality have a positive effect on many psychosocial and health-related outcomes across the lifespan (e.g., Fabricatore et al., 2000; Fry, 2000; Mueller et al., 2001; George et al., 2002). ; Levin and Chatters, 2008; Krause, 2011; VanderWeele, 2017).

15. Formal, Corporate, and Extrovert Expression

As a result of the complexity of the concepts of religiosity and spirituality, it turns out that it is crucial to define how these ideas are imagined in various written works. According to Pargament (1997), religiosity and spirituality are aimed in terms of an individual's values, beliefs, behaviors, and identity and may focus on the sacred or functional aspects of religion. In other words, an individual's values, beliefs, behaviors and identity constitute his or her religiosity and spirituality.

more specific , on the one hand, religiosity is often seen and typically functionalized as the "official, institutional, and outward expression" of one's relationship with the sacred (Cotton et al., 2006, p. 472). This issue, as beliefs and practices associated with a particular religious worldview and community, is a subject of separate study. Religiosity, on the other hand, is often seen as "official, institutional, and outward expression" (Cotton et al. (Iannello et al., 2019) for a personal connection with transcendent realities and a reciprocal connection with humanity (Zinnbauer et al., 1999; Benson and Roehlkepartain , 2008; Worthington et al., 2011). Therefore, it is transcendence, introspection, interconnectedness, and the search for meaning in life (King & Boyatzis , 2015), (Benson et al., 2003).

There is a relationship between religiosity, spirituality, and one's own sense of happiness.

Although the findings of different studies do not always agree with each other, it has been shown that both spirituality and religion are positive predictors of SL (Kim- Prieto & Miller, 2018). In terms of the cognitive part of SDL , many studies have shown a beneficial link between spirituality and religiosity and life satisfaction (Yoon & Lee, 2004). To account for these findings, it was assumed that individuals who felt a stronger connection and direction with a higher power, i.e., an elevated level of religious and spiritual involvement, tended to be more optimistic. perspectives on their own lives (Vishkin et al., 2016, 2019; Ramsay et al., 2019). Having the awareness that one relates to a greater power, with other people and with life in general, is an effective way to keep a positive outlook on one's life, despite being exposed to a variety of challenges. Participation

in religious and spiritual practices can also be beneficial for people's lives, as it can strengthen both an individual's internal resources (such as a sense of self-worth) and social resources (such as a sense of belonging to a network) (Lim & Putnam , 2010).

This idea receives greater support from the role of religious beliefs and practices, which are often associated with a positive relationship with levels of life satisfaction (Koenig & Larson, 2001; Abu- Raiya et al., 2015; Krause , 2015). Having strongly held views, whether of God's existence or non-existence, can have a beneficial effect on an individual's well-being by lowering cognitive dissonance levels. This can be the case regardless of what belief you hold. People may be more likely to feel a state of psychological tension in a lack of subjective certainty and be motivated to relieve that stress (Kahneman et al., 1982; Kitchens and Phillips, 2018). According to Galen and Kloet's research, religious people and non-religious people can be fairly compared in terms of the strength of their faith, and both report equal levels of well-being. This may be one of the explanations underlying this finding (2011).

16. Conclusion

To better understand the role religiosity plays, it is also crucial to consider how the specific background culture conceptualizes religiosity. For example, Graham and Crown (2014) analyzed a large dataset of more than 160 countries and found that there was an overall positive correlation between religiosity and the degree of this correlation varied by culture. To be more specific , religiosity had a stronger effect on SWB in cultures with high religiosity than in cultures with low religiosity. To the same conclusion , Stavrova et al. (2013) analyzed data from European and World Values Studies. They found that the predictive power of religiosity on life satisfaction was higher in cultures that placed a high value on religion, while the relationship was negative in cultures that placed a high value on atheism. The authors attributed this finding to the use of highly religious cultures' European and World Values Studies datasets.

Schools do not only serve to teach children new knowledge; it also promotes a sense of community and togetherness among both students and staff working there. It is possible to create a more positive environment for learning by connecting students with different beliefs through religious education. It has been shown that students who receive religious education have a more meaningful purpose in life and receive more social support from their classmates . It also has the potential to serve as a vehicle for spreading religious ideas and practices that encourage people to look after and help one another. Positive mental health and general well-being are associated with both participation in religious communities and the performance of religious rituals . Both being part of a religious community and actively taking part in religious practices offer opportunities for individuals to receive social support. The idea of love and brotherhood fostered by religious teachings is one of the main contributors to the positive impact of religiosity on well-being. This social support is primarily responsible for the impact of religion on well-being. According to research, taking part in religious practices has been shown to have positive effects on adolescents, including higher self-esteem levels and lower rates of substance abuse . Additionally, taking part in religious practices helped adolescents gain a sense of belonging that contributed to these positive outcomes. Additionally, social interactions that develop because of taking part in religious activities have also been shown to interfere with adolescent suicidal thoughts.

17. Source

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